

Easy Hilbert

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The Hilbert transform of suitable signals is formally a convolution with a singular kernel **[1]**:

$$H\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S} * \mathbf{1}/\mathbf{x}$$

In practice, numerical estimation is done in the Fourier domain using the symbol property:

$$\widehat{H(\mathbf{S})}(\omega) = -i\text{sgn}(\omega)\hat{\mathbf{S}}(\omega)$$

But estimation in the signal domain can also be numerically practical; let's test this on the signals

$$s = \sin(t), \quad c = \cos(t)$$

since we know that

$$H\sin(t) = -\cos(t), \quad H\cos(t) = \sin(t)$$

The key is the kernel **k**; but that is simplicity itself:

$$\mathbf{k} = [-1 \ 1]; \text{ 'Easy Hilbert' : } \mathbf{h}(\cdot) = \text{conv}(\mathbf{k}, \cdot)$$

In OCTAVE code

```
k = [-1 1];, r = .01; , t = r:r:2*pi; , len = length(t);  
s = sin(t); , c = cos(t);  
hs = conv(k, s)/r; % should yield -cos(t)  
hs = hs(2:len-1); % remove endpoints  
hc = conv(k, c)/r; % should yield sin(t)  
hc = hc(2:len-1); % remove endpoints
```

Output is plotted below; $H\sin(t)$ in the top panel using the 'Easy Hilbert' convolution transform of $\sin(t)$, scaled by the sampling rate; similarly $H\cos(t)$ is in the second panel.

The harmonic surrogates **hs** and **hc** are (practically) orthogonal, out-of-phase by $\pi/2$, and in quadrature; thus

$$(hs, hc) \approx -.0036923$$

and

$$hs^2 + hc^2 = 1$$

Their complex extension here would be

$$zh = -hs + i hc$$

and the OCTAVE command

```
rate=diff(unwrap(angle(zh)));
```

revealed a constant rate of .01, the sampling rate **r** as expected.

However, neither surrogate is orthogonal or in quadrature with its parent; thus

$$(s, hs) \approx 1.5555, \quad (c, hc) \approx 1.5745$$

although the dispersion of quadratures is relatively small:

$$\text{std}(c^2 + hc^2) = \text{std}(s^2 + hs^2) \approx .0035449$$

As for mixed-complex extensions, let

$$z1 = c + i hc$$

$$z2 = -hs + i s$$

While the rate extraction from **z1** (for example) isn't constant, its mean is accurate:

$$\text{mean}(\text{diff}(\text{unwrap}(\text{angle}(z1)))) = .01$$

and dispersion is small:

$$\text{std}(\text{diff}(\text{unwrap}(\text{angle}(z1)))) \approx .000035477$$

So, given an arbitrary AMFM digital signal **S_n**, the complex extension

$$Z_n = S_n + i h(S_n)$$

where $h(\cdot)$ is now the 'Easy Hilbert' formulation presented above, should allow estimation of harmonic features.

As a test case, consider the female voice file 'faks' from the TIMIT database, sampled at 8 KHz; the waveform is displayed below.

Signal energy (in dB) and Instantaneous Frequency (unscaled) estimated in blocks of .01 sec (80 samples) are displayed below:

These results match up very well with estimates using the 'hilbert' function in OCTAVE.

Code generating these estimates is included below for completeness.

```
len=length(sig); % sig is the voice file 'faks'
k=[-1 1];
blok=80;
last=floor(len/blok);
for j=1:last
cut=sig(1+(j-1)*blok:j*blok);
hil=conv(k,cut); % Easy Hilbert here
hil=hil(1:blok); % Endpoint removal
z=cut+i*hil; % Complex extension
eng(j)=10*log10(mean(abs(z))); % In dB units
inst(j)=mean(diff unwrap(angle(z)))); % Unscaled
end
```

Reference

A. Cusmariu, 'Fractional Analytic Signals', <https://zenodo.org/records/3953020>, 20 July, 2020